

MAIN ARTICLE

Preparing for pandemic response in the context of limited resources

Jair Andrade,^{a*} Berend Beishuizen,^b Mart Stein,^b Máire Connolly^c and Jim Duggan^a

Abstract

Pandemics are outbreaks of an infectious disease that increase morbidity and mortality over a wide geographic area. These events require large-scale interventions from governments and health agencies to curtail transmission within a population. In assessing the impact of these interventions, policymakers avail themselves of simulations from compartmental models. However, it is commonplace that modellers employ fixed fractions to represent interventions, which implicitly assume that resources instantaneously and boundlessly adjust to the desired target and may predict overly optimistic outcomes. Here, we propose a model that integrates four crucial countermeasures subject to resource constraints. We present this structure utilising the concept of small models and frame the simulations in the context of a hypothetical spread of influenza in the Netherlands, drawing on empirical data. After incorporating resource constraints, we find that only a comprehensive response controls the disease. These findings highlight the need for improving strategic plans to support pandemic preparedness.

Copyright © 2024 The Authors. *System Dynamics Review* published by John Wiley & Sons Ltd on behalf of System Dynamics Society.

Syst. Dyn. Rev. (2024)

Additional Supporting Information may be found online in the supporting information tab for this article.

Introduction

Pandemics are large-scale outbreaks of an infectious disease that lead to increases in morbidity and mortality over a wide geographic area (Morens *et al.*, 2009). These seismic events have threatened human populations throughout history, and the risk of future pandemics has continued to increase over the past century due to the globalisation of trade, travel, and technology, land use changes, and natural environment exploitation (Marani *et al.*, 2021). In the last two decades, transmissible pathogens have caused three pandemics (Lee and McKibbin, 2004; Shrestha *et al.*, 2011; Wang *et al.*, 2022) and several cross-border epidemics (Gessain *et al.*, 2022; Shultz *et al.*, 2015), causing major disruption and substantial health and economic costs (Douglas *et al.*, 2020). For instance, the rapid spread of SARS-CoV-2 in early 2020 forced governments to implement unprecedented social-distancing measures, placing half of the global population under strict forms of home confinement (Di Domenico *et al.*, 2020).

Naturally, one wonders what could be done better if another pandemic occurs. Compartmental models offer a valuable tool for exploring this question as they

^a Data Science Institute and School of Computer Science, University of Galway, Galway, Ireland

^b National Institute for Public Health and the Environment, Bilthoven, The Netherlands

^c School of Health Sciences, University of Galway, Galway, Ireland

* Correspondence to: Jair Andrade, University of Galway, University Rd, Galway, Ireland.

E-mail: jair.andrade@universityofgalway.ie

Accepted by Hazhir Rahmandad, Received 26 August 2023; Revised 19 January 2024 and 9 April 2024; Accepted 28 April 2024

make fundamental assumptions explicit in a logical framework (Homer, 1996), allowing for rigorous evaluation of public health interventions. Nevertheless, building a single model for every possible pandemic threat is infeasible. While the standard framework commonly used to represent infectious disease dynamics can be adapted to various pathogens, such as measles (Lloyd, 2001; Keeling and Grenfell, 2002; Krylova and Earn, 2013), COVID-19 (Davies *et al.*, 2020a; Duggan *et al.*, 2024; Gleeson *et al.*, 2022), and influenza (Andrade and Duggan, 2020, 2021; Vynnycky and Edmunds, 2008), each disease possesses its own intricacies that require customisation. Nonetheless, insights obtained from one disease can inform the management of other diseases.

Specifically, we focus on pandemic influenza on the grounds that these unpredictable but recurring events can have significant global consequences (World Health Organization, 2017). In fact, influenza strains have been responsible for causing four pandemics over the last century (Monto and Fukuda, 2019), including the devastating H1N1 pandemic in 1918 that led to the death of an estimated 50 million people, especially among young adults and children (Monto and Webster, 2013). Established measures to mitigate the impact of influenza viruses on individuals and communities involve pharmaceutical (Daems *et al.*, 2005; Monto, 2003) and nonpharmaceutical interventions (Rashid *et al.*, 2015; Vynnycky and Edmunds, 2008). In the literature, several works showcase methodologies to represent countermeasures such as testing, tracing and isolation (Davies *et al.*, 2020b; Eames and Keeling, 2003; Fraser *et al.*, 2004; Sturniolo *et al.*, 2021), mobility restrictions (Andrade and Duggan, 2022; Davies *et al.*, 2020a; Vynnycky and Edmunds, 2008) and vaccination (Duintjer Tebbens *et al.*, 2005; Mossong *et al.*, 1999; Rahmandad, 2022).

Despite the abundance of literature, models seldom explicitly account for the (availability of) resources that underpin and, more importantly, constrain the policies under evaluation (Auping *et al.*, 2017). Instead, it is commonplace to represent resource capacity as a fixed percentage of its demand (Bushman *et al.*, 2021; Di Domenico *et al.*, 2020; Flahault *et al.*, 2006; Halloran *et al.*, 2008; Hollingsworth *et al.*, 2011; Teslya *et al.*, 2020). Based on our experience, we presume that modellers follow this approach because of the paucity of readily available estimates of resource capacity. To circumvent this difficulty, a fixed percentage serves as a mathematically convenient tool that facilitates the exploration of diverse scenarios via sensitivity analyses. Employing this tool, though, implies that regardless of changes in the system, the interventions' effect remains constant during their implementation. Therefore, one implicitly assumes that resources instantaneously and boundlessly adjust to their demand.

However, as the system dynamics tradition has long emphasised, resources are stock variables that accumulate over time at different speeds (Ghaffarzadegan *et al.*, 2023). From a resource-based viewpoint (Barney, 1991; Peteraf, 1993), variation in performance relates to the differences in the rate at which organisations build and maintain their capacity. In the case of pandemic management, the performance of public health response depends on the level of readily available personnel, physical infrastructure, and standard operating procedures to utilise capacity effectively. Since it takes substantial time to accumulate these resources—far more than the time a pandemic pathogen requires to infect the entire population—the number of resources available during the response phase

reflects the level of prior investment and strategic planning undertaken in the preparedness phase.

Therefore, this article aims to contribute to the existing literature by building upon earlier work (Krumkamp *et al.*, 2011; Stein *et al.*, 2012; Yañez *et al.*, 2017) to formulate a compartmental model with explicit structures that account for countermeasures constrained by finite resources. This formulation provides a means to conduct realistic assessments of the potential effectiveness of interventions, highlighting the importance of installed capacity in managing infectious diseases. In doing so, we stress the significance of the preparedness phase's role in the successful containment and mitigation of a pandemic.

Nevertheless, modelling a comprehensive response entails a complex structure comprising a large number of stocks and feedback loops, which are challenging to maintain, interpret, and explain (Lane, 1992). Therefore, we present this model incrementally and sequentially, compounding the effect of each intervention onto the previous one. Furthermore, we leverage the concept of *small, powerful models* (Ghaffarzadegan *et al.*, 2011) to describe the rationale of each countermeasure when subjected to resource constraints. These *digestible* structures, in turn, facilitate model validation (Barlas, 1996) precisely because it is easier to isolate the source of implausible behaviour when investigated in a small piece of structure than when examined in a larger and more complex one (Homer, 2012; Sterman, 2000). In doing so, we build up a library of simulation models that will be a valuable resource for system dynamics practitioners with a broad spectrum of expertise interested in modelling infectious diseases.

We frame this work as a case-based modelling approach (Ghaffarzadegan *et al.*, 2023), drawing upon knowledge gained from past crises. This knowledge has emerged as a result of a project which brings together expertise from a number of European national public health agencies, aiming to enhance capacity for pandemic preparedness and response. In particular, we explore plausible scenarios of a hypothetical spread of a novel pandemic influenza virus in the Netherlands. Since there are no readily available estimates of resource capacity in the event of a new pandemic, we leverage empirical open data collected by the Dutch public health system during the COVID-19 response. This data also includes estimates of behavioural compliance towards countermeasures. We build the models in *Stella* (see Systems, 2022) and run the simulations in *R* (R Core Team, 2023). The code is freely available at <https://github.com/jandraor/preparedness>. In the following section, we describe the simulation model in detail.

SEI3R profile (no intervention)

To represent the transmission of an infectious disease, modellers stratify individuals according to their infection status and describe, through equations, the transitions of individuals between compartments. These transitions can be stochastic or deterministic. The former employs continuous time Markov chains or stochastic differential equations (Allen, 2017) to introduce randomness into the system. Stochastic models are preferred for addressing questions involving small populations and analysing the persistence of infections (Keeling and

Grenfell, 2002; Vynnycky and White, 2010), but they can also be used for studying large populations (Camacho *et al.*, 2014).

On the other hand, deterministic structures (Anderson and May, 1992) formulated via *ordinary differential equations* (ODEs) may enable sufficient biological understanding of the system, provided that population numbers never become too small (Renshaw, 1993), that is, ODE models are appropriate for relatively large populations (Heesterbeek and Dietz, 1996), where the average behaviour of the system can be described with high accuracy (Keeling and Rohani, 2008). Undoubtedly, the main advantage of deterministic models is their mathematical convenience, which allows various kinds of studies, such as disease characterisation (van den Driessche, 2017), stability (Krylova and Earn, 2013; Strogatz, 2018), sensitivity (Epstein *et al.*, 2021), and simulation analyses (Andrade and Duggan, 2023; Gostic *et al.*, 2020; Park and Bolker, 2020). These studies facilitate the identification and interpretation of cause-and-effect relationships. Given these advantages and the fact that this study focuses on large-scale outbreaks, we opt for a deterministic model.

Specifically, we adopt an extended version of the SEIR framework (*SEI3R profile*) to represent the dynamics of a novel pandemic influenza virus. Under this profile (Figure 1), we stratify individuals as susceptible (S_t), exposed (E_t), infectious, and recovered (R_t). We further divide the infectious class by medical status, resulting in three compartments: preclinical (Gu *et al.*, 2011; Thompson *et al.*, 2016), clinical, and subclinical or asymptomatic (Chowell *et al.*, 2006; Chowell *et al.*, 2007), denoted by P_t , I_t , and A_t , respectively. In this model (Eq. 1), we assume that individuals are initially susceptible (S_t) and become exposed (E_t) at a rate λ_t (force of infection) following effective contact (B_t) with an infectious person (I_t , P_t , A_t). After a latent period (σ^{-1}), exposed individuals become infectious. A fraction (ω) of these individuals will remain asymptomatic for ν^{-1} days before developing clinical symptoms. In other words, they transition from preclinical (P_t) to clinical (I_t). On average, the latter stage lasts for γ^{-1} days. On the other hand, the remaining fraction ($1 - \omega$) develops none or mild symptoms throughout its infectious phase (subclinical). Individuals on this path cease to transmit the disease after κ^{-1} days and are relatively (η) less contagious than their counterparts on the clinical path. Then, individuals from both paths eventually converge to the recovered state (R_t), where they are immune to reinfection (Barry *et al.*, 2008).

$$\begin{aligned}
 \dot{S}_t &= -\lambda_t S_t \\
 \dot{E}_t &= \lambda_t S_t - \sigma E_t \\
 \dot{P}_t &= \omega \sigma E_t - \nu P_t \\
 \dot{I}_t &= \nu P_t - \gamma I_t \\
 \dot{A}_t &= (1 - \omega) \sigma E_t - \kappa A_t \\
 \dot{R}_t &= \gamma I_t + \kappa A_t \\
 \dot{C}_t &= \lambda_t S_t \\
 \lambda_t &= \frac{B_t(P_t + \eta I_t + A_t)}{N}
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Fig. 1. Stock-and-flow diagram of the SEI3R profile. Red indicates infectious compartments. Feedback loops are omitted to improve clarity. (S, Susceptible; E, Exposed; P, Preclinical infectious; I, Clinical infectious; A, Subclinical infectious; R, Recovered)

Moreover, our model excludes natural demography and disease-induced mortality. The outbreak’s timescale is much faster than the characteristic times of demographic processes (births and deaths), justifying this exclusion. Similarly, excluding disease-induced mortality has minimal impact on the system’s dynamics but facilitates the inclusion of further complexities. Details are provided in Appendix S1 (Section 2.2) in the online supporting information. These assumptions imply that the population size (N) remains constant over the simulation period. Finally, \dot{C}_t denotes the rate of new cases per day and C_t its accumulation (cumulative cases). When normalised by population size, these quantities become the incidence ($\frac{\dot{C}_t}{N}$) and attack ($c_t = \frac{C_t}{N}$) rates. Due to its small magnitude, the incidence rate is scaled up by a factor of 1000. Then, we configure this profile’s parameters (including initial conditions) to values that reflect the spread of influenza. Estimates of biological constants (Table 1) and population values can be obtained from the literature and demographic studies, respectively. Regarding initial conditions, since we assume that the pandemic is caused by a novel strain of influenza and triggered by a patient zero, all states are set to zero, except for S_0 and P_0 , which are initialised at $N - 1$ and 1, respectively.

Initially, we assume that the transmission rate is time invariant ($B_t = \beta$). This assumption entails an inaction state (from individuals and the public health system) to the surge of cases and serves as a benchmark against which the performance of countermeasures can be quantified. We draw on the concept of the basic reproduction number (\mathfrak{R}_0) to approximate the value of β . In epidemiology, one defines \mathfrak{R}_0 as the average number of secondary infections arising from the introduction of one infected individual into a totally susceptible population (Anderson and May, 1992). This quantity characterises the dynamics of compartmental models through a *threshold phenomenon* (Heffernan *et al.*, 2005). If $\mathfrak{R}_0 > 1$, the pathogen can invade a susceptible population. Furthermore, its magnitude gauges the transmission potential of an emerging infectious disease (Heffernan *et al.*, 2005) and the effort required to control it (Wallinga and Lipsitch, 2007). Namely, diseases with a higher \mathfrak{R}_0 are expected to result in a greater number of individuals experiencing infection during the course of a pandemic (House *et al.*, 2013).

Table 1. Biological parameters for pandemic influenza

Parameter	Description	Value	Unit	Source
σ^{-1}	Mean latent period	2.00	Days	Anderson and May (1992)
ν^{-1}	Mean preclinical period	1.00	Day	Gu <i>et al.</i> (2011)
γ^{-1}	Mean clinical period	2.00	Days	Anderson and May (1992)
κ^{-1}	Mean subclinical period	3.00	Days	$\nu^{-1} + \gamma^{-1}$
ω	Clinical fraction	0.84	Days	Leung <i>et al.</i> (2015)
η	Relative infectiousness	0.50	Unitless	Halloran <i>et al.</i> (2008)

One can formulate \mathfrak{R}_0 as a function of a compartmental model's parameters using the next-generation matrix method (Brouwer, 2022; Diekmann *et al.*, 1990; van den Driessche, 2017). Equation 2 corresponds to such analytical expression obtained for the *SEI3R* profile. This equation indicates that \mathfrak{R}_0 depends upon the biological parameters (for which we already have estimates) and β . Therefore, one only needs to find configurations of β that produce plausible \mathfrak{R}_0 values for pandemic influenza. Based on the literature (Chowell *et al.*, 2007; Mills *et al.*, 2004), such values are situated between 2 and 4. Figure 2 shows 1000 simulations of the *SEI3R* profile whose basic reproduction number conforms to those bounds. These results indicate that if the disease is let to run its course, between 80% and 98% of the Dutch population could be infected at the end of the pandemic.

$$\mathfrak{R}_0 = \beta[\omega(\gamma^{-1} + \nu^{-1}) + (1 - \omega)\eta\kappa^{-1}] \quad (2)$$

Control strategies

In epidemiological terms, one can equate pandemic management to controlling the *effective* reproduction number (Thompson *et al.*, 2019). This quantity, denoted by \mathfrak{R}_t , is defined as the *time-varying* average number of secondary cases caused by a primary case at a calendar time t (Anderson and May, 1992; Gostic *et al.*, 2020), and it is a theoretical indicator of the course of an infectious process (Vynnycky and White, 2010). This time-dependent variation (Nishiura and Chowell, 2009) of the disease's transmission potential (Eq. 3) occurs due to the decline in susceptible individuals (s_t) and changes in contact patterns due to external interventions (ε_t). Interestingly, \mathfrak{R}_t generalises the threshold phenomenon at any time of the epidemic. If $\mathfrak{R}_t > 1$, each infectious person leads to more than one secondary infectious person, and the disease is (re)emerging (Brett *et al.*, 2020); below that threshold, there is limited secondary transmission, and the number of new cases begins to decline until the disease disappears. From a practical perspective, policymakers aim to introduce policies that bring \mathfrak{R}_t below the epidemiological threshold in order to control the disease.

$$\mathfrak{R}_t = s_t \varepsilon_t \mathfrak{R}_0 \quad (3)$$

$$s_t = \frac{S_t}{N}$$

Fig. 2. No intervention. This plot shows the attack rate (cumulative cases normalised by population size) from 1000 simulations of an SEI3R model configured with an effective contact rate (β) ranging between 0.7 and 1.4. These configurations yield a basic reproduction number between 2 and 4

Nonpharmaceutical interventions

Specifically, ε_t in Eq. 3 denotes *nonpharmaceutical interventions (NPIs)*. These countermeasures aim to reduce the number of effective contacts between infectious and susceptible persons, thereby reducing the spread of infection, the peak demand for hospital beds, and deaths (World Health Organization, 2019). NPIs can be broadly classified into *International Travel-Related Measures* (Ryu *et al.*, 2020), *Personal Protective and Environmental Measures* (Xiao *et al.*, 2020), and *Social-Distancing Measures* (Fong *et al.*, 2020). Due to inconclusive evidence regarding the effectiveness of international travel-related measures and personal protective and environmental measures in controlling influenza transmission (Flahault *et al.*, 2006; Ryu *et al.*, 2020; Xiao *et al.*, 2020), we focus our model on social-distancing measures. Of note, it is not contended whether masks can reduce the risk of infection. They can certainly do so. However, their impact is severely limited by a lack of proper use and compliance (Howard *et al.*, 2021).

Testing and isolation

In all influenza epidemics and pandemics, the initial recommendation from public health authorities is to advise individuals with a positive diagnosis to isolate themselves at home for a certain period to prevent further contact and subsequent onward transmission (World Health Organization, 2019). We model this intervention, known as *Testing and Isolation (T&I)*, by assuming that individuals with clinical symptoms seek diagnostic testing and adhere to isolation protocols. Based on this assumption, we disaggregate the SEI3R's clinical path (Figure 3) into two *quasi-equivalent* streams (*undiagnosed* and *diagnosed*). The former stream corresponds to the existing stocks P_t and I_t , whereas the latter corresponds to two additional stocks (P_t^d and I_t^d) representing the diagnosed class. It is important to note that individuals are typically identified after they have completed their preclinical period, during which they have had regular contact with others. However, as it will become apparent in the next section, keeping a record of these *eventually diagnosed* preclinical individuals is necessary. These streams only differ in the contribution of diagnosed clinical individuals (I_t^d) to the force of infection, who limit their movements after receiving a diagnostic test and, thus, transmit the pathogen to a lesser degree than their counterparts in the undetected

Fig. 3. Testing and isolation's stock and flow diagram. Blue indicates the added structure. Red indicates infectious compartments (Pd, Preclinical infectious diagnosed; Id, Clinical infectious diagnosed)

stream. We assume that the magnitude of such relative contribution is inversely proportional to individual compliance (t^d) — that is, the percentage of people going into isolation if positive. This value fluctuated between 43% and 61% in the Netherlands during the COVID-19 pandemic (VWS, 2023a), and for simplicity, we assume the midpoint value. See the complete set of equations in Appendix S2 (section 1) in the online supporting information.

Moreover, the fraction of diagnosed individuals among those who become symptomatic, or the testing fraction (θ), determines the magnitude of the flows passing through both streams. A typical strategy to explore the effect of *T&I* consists of assuming a constant θ and configuring it to various levels between 0% and 100%, where a higher value indicates a larger capacity. For example, Di Domenico *et al.* (2020) employed three levels of testing (25%, 50%, and 75%) in a COVID-19 study. Likewise, Sturniolo *et al.* (2021) performed a sensitivity analysis using values between 0% and 50%. In influenza analyses, various values have been considered (60% and 80% by Halloran *et al.* (2008), whereas Flahault *et al.* (2006) were more conservative with a 10% testing fraction). Following this regime, we simulate the *T&I* structure under three scenarios of testing intensity (0%, 25%, 50%), assuming $\mathfrak{R}_0 = 3$. Notice that the first scenario corresponds to a no-intervention situation, which we refer to as the *base-case* scenario. As expected, the simulations validate the premise that higher testing intensity reduces the number of cases, as evidenced in the top plot of Figure 4a (grey lines). Allowing the infection to run its course results in an attack rate of 94% by day 150, whereas a testing intensity of 25% and 50% decreases this indicator to 92% and 90%, respectively. In terms of absolute numbers, a testing intensity of 50% prevents nearly 800,000 people from acquiring the infection.

Nevertheless, as mentioned earlier, fixed fractions entail the unrealistic assumption that resource capacity instantaneously and boundlessly adjusts to its demand. On the contrary, there are upper limits to the capacity of test centres and existing diagnostic laboratories in terms of personnel, reagents, machines, and other materials. Salathé *et al.* (2020, p. 2) acknowledge that during the COVID-19 pandemic, “the disruption to the production and supply of laboratory reagents only a few weeks into the epidemic shows how severely global diagnostic preparedness has been neglected in recent years.” Nevertheless, modelling the

Fig. 4. (a) Testing and Isolation. This plot compares the assumptions of constant (grey lines) and time-varying (blue line) testing fractions in a SEI3R model that only incorporates T&I. We illustrate the effect on the attack and testing rates (top two time series). The third time series shows the dynamics of available testing capacity when modelled with the logistic function. The bottom time series compares testing fractions from both assumptions. (b) Testing, tracing, and isolation. This plot compares the assumptions of constant (grey lines) and time-varying (blue line) testing and tracing fractions in a SEI3R model that incorporates T&I and CT, namely TTI. We illustrate the effect on the attack and tracing rates (top two time series). The third time series depicts the dynamics of available tracing capacity when modelled using the logistic function. The bottom time series compares tracing fractions from both assumptions. In the case of constant fractions, we assumed identical values for testing and tracing fractions per scenario. For instance, the dotted line indicates that testing and tracing fractions were configured at 25% each. (c) Effective reproduction number for the scenario with time-varying fractions. The dot-dash line indicates the basic reproduction number

intricate dynamics of supply chains and human resource management is an endeavour in its own right.

Thus, the challenge faced by a modeller lies in capturing the effect of these numerous factors while avoiding the temptation to build excessively detailed models that may lead to a false sense of accuracy (Keeling and Rohani, 2008). Consequently, we formulate the time-varying testing fraction (θ_t) in terms of a

simple structure that accounts for the realistic features of the system (Eq. 4) — that is, a ratio between actual testing and potential demand (D_t^d). Actual testing refers to the minimum between the number of people seeking a diagnostic test (δD_t^d) and the public health system's testing capacity. In this formulation, δ denotes the willingness of individuals to take a test if they have symptoms, which in the Netherlands varied between 30% and 90% during the COVID-19 pandemic (VWS, 2023a). In this case, we assume the midpoint value. On the other hand, Q_t^d denotes testing capacity whose dynamics follow the logistic growth model, and its units are expressed in daily tests per 1000 population.

$$\theta_t = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{for } D_t^d = 0 \\ \frac{\min\left(\delta D_t^d, \frac{Q_t^d N}{1000}\right)}{D_t^d}, & \text{for } D_t^d > 0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$D_t^d = \omega \sigma E_t$$

First suggested by Verhulst (Bacaër, 2011), the logistic growth model (Eq. 5) was formulated to describe population dynamics characterised by an initial stage of approximately exponential growth. Then, this growth decelerates as the population approaches the carrying capacity (saturation), flattening the curve and yielding the characteristic *S-shaped* behaviour over time. We posit this logistic structure as a cogent formulation to represent resource dynamics. Under this interpretation, Q_t represents available capacity, the level of resources that can be actively employed at a given time; ρ corresponds to the daily growth in availability, and α represents potential capacity, the maximum level the public system can utilise.

$$\dot{Q}_t = \rho Q_t \left(1 - \frac{Q_t}{\alpha}\right) \quad (5)$$

Notice that these last two parameters serve as preparedness indicators. On the one hand, α gauges the level of investment in infrastructure and skilled workforce. On the other hand, ρ represents the velocity at which the public health system converts potential capacity into available capacity. This velocity, in turn, reflects the quality of standard operating procedures. We assume that α is constant based on the fact that the time scale of pandemics is much faster than the characteristic times for building infrastructure and training personnel.

Regarding ρ , the literature associates this rate with responsiveness to risk (Rahmandad *et al.*, 2021; Rahmandad, 2022; Rahmandad *et al.*, 2022). That is, as the number of infections and deaths rise, governments perceive a higher level of risk, leading to higher usage of resources and vice versa. Considering that this work aims to evaluate the impact of resource constraints, for simplicity, we omit the risk-driven response feedback. In other words, following the first case, we assume that the public health system increases available capacity as swiftly as possible, irrespective of incidence and mortality levels.

To configure the logistic structure, we derive estimates for initial (Q_0) and potential capacity (α) from the Dutch open data (VWS, 2023b), whereas the growth rate (ρ) was approximated through model calibration (see Appendix S2 in the online supporting information). Simulating the $T&I$ structure under the constraint imposed by the logistic formulation (blue lines in Figure 4a) reveals that when the number of cases is relatively small, the public health system can meet the testing demand. Nevertheless, as the number of cases rises, the capacity saturates to the point of collapse. Notice the trough in the testing fraction, starting around day 40 and reaching a level (1% around day 60) substantially lower than the scenarios with a fixed fraction (25%, 50%). Consequently, the attack rate in the scenario with a time-varying fraction in the early days resembles that of the scenario with a fixed 50% testing intensity, but as time progresses, it aligns more closely with the base-case scenario (0%). In short, this comparison highlights that assuming a fixed testing fraction may underestimate capacity during periods of low demand or be overly optimistic during the peak of cases.

Contact tracing

In addition to isolating symptomatic individuals, public health authorities can also conduct a search to identify those who may have contracted the infection through close contact with a confirmed case. These traced individuals are then advised to undergo quarantine as a preventive measure against the further spread of the disease (Thomas Craig *et al.*, 2021). This approach, known as *contact tracing* (CT), is recommended in suspected human cases of influenza (Eames *et al.*, 2010). We model this intervention (Figure 5) by extending the $T&I$ structure (Figure 3) following the assumption that when someone tests positive, she or he recalls her or his contacts during the preclinical phase; hence, the need for splitting the clinical path into two streams at the preclinical stage. Since contact tracing always encompasses the effect of $T&I$, we refer to this extension as testing, tracing, and isolation (TTI). The reader can find the complete set of equations in Appendix S2 (section 2) in the online supporting information.

In the TTI model, it is assumed that effective contacts originating from the diagnosed preclinical class correspond to the demand for contact tracing. Contact-traced individuals, if infected, flow through the stream of *infected in quarantine* (additional upper path highlighted in blue in Figure 5) until they recover. On the other hand, contact-traced individuals who remain susceptible stay in quarantine until they have completed the recommended quarantine period (additional path on the left highlighted in blue in Figure 5). Lastly, unidentified contacts who acquire the disease flow through the existing paths (grey paths in Figure 5). Regarding transmission dynamics, contact tracing has a dual effect on the effective reproduction number. Firstly, it temporarily reduces the susceptible fraction *participating* in the contagion process by quarantining uninfected individuals following close contact. Secondly, it lowers the overall force of infection by contact-traced infectious individuals compliant with public health recommendations.

In a manner analogous to the $T&I$ structure, we simulate the TTI model under two assumptions of resource constraints (Figure 4b): fixed fractions and logistic growth. For the former, we assign identical values to testing and contact tracing intensities per simulation. For the latter, referred to as *Ref TTI*, contact-tracing

Fig. 5. Stock-and-flow diagram of contact tracing. Blue denotes the added structure, whereas red denotes infectious compartments. (Aq: subclinical infectious in quarantine; Eq: exposed in quarantine; Iq: clinical infectious in quarantine; Pq: preclinical infectious in quarantine; Sq, susceptible in quarantine)

parameters are estimated from publicly available data (GGD, 2020). See Appendix S2 in the online supporting information for more details. These results reinforce the findings from the previous section. While a 50% fixed intensity reduces the attack rate at day 150 from 94% to 78% (i.e., 3 million fewer infected people), the model that incorporates the logistic structure outperforms its counterpart with fixed fractions only in the early stage of the pandemic, but the outcome at day 150 is similar to that of the no-intervention scenario (0%). In epidemiological terms, TTI lowers \mathcal{R}_t from 3 to 2.25 (Figure 4c) while it can handle the resource demand. Nevertheless, the growth of cases eventually overwhelms contact-tracing capacity, collapsing the tracing fraction to a minimum of 3% and pushing \mathcal{R}_t near the no-intervention scenario, allowing the infection to run its course.

While the *Ref TTI* scenario indicates that testing and tracing mainly produce a delaying effect, it provides additional time for developing more sustainable interventions. Therefore, exploring strategies to maximise the impact of TTI is worthwhile. For instance, enhancing standard operating procedures can expedite the time required to utilise all potential capacity within the system. Furthermore, investment in physical resources and personnel training can increase such potential capacity. Consequently, we formulate three additional resource scenarios for each intervention (Table 2) that, when combined, yield nine simulations. To formulate these scenarios, we take the estimated capacities from the Dutch data as a reference (grey lines in Figure 6a,b) and double the growth rate ($2\hat{\rho}$) in Scenario 1. In Scenario 2, we assume that the public health system harnesses entirely its resources from the start. Similarly, Scenario 3 assumes that the level of resources is twice that of Scenario 2. For example, $t2$ and $c2$ denote Scenario 2 applied to testing and tracing resources, respectively.

Since this sensitivity analysis aims to explore the impact of various resource levels on TTI 's delaying effect, we use the incidence rate as the performance indicator. Beginning with the $t1$ scenario (beige lines in Figure 6c), note that doubling the testing capacity's growth rate reinforces the delay effect and lowers the peak compared to the *Ref TTI* scenario (grey line). Of course, even greater peak reduction is achievable if testing is always performed at its estimated potential capacity

Table 2. Capacity scenarios

Scenario	Initial Capacity	Growth Rate	Maximum Capacity
1	\hat{Q}_0	$2\hat{\rho}$	$\hat{\alpha}$
2	$\hat{\alpha}$	0	$\hat{\alpha}$
3	$2\hat{\alpha}$	0	$2\hat{\alpha}$

Fig. 6. Sensitivity analysis of resource capacity. (a) Testing capacity scenarios. The grey line denotes the scenario obtained from the empirical data, and the coloured lines indicate alternative scenarios $t1$, $t2$, and $t3$ (see Table 2). (b) Tracing capacity scenarios. The grey line denotes the scenario obtained from the empirical data, and the coloured lines indicate alternative scenarios $c1$, $c2$, and $c3$ (see Table 2). (c) Effect of resource capacity on the incidence rate. This plot presents nine alternative scenarios of resource capacity (coloured lines) compared against a reference simulation, which is obtained from a model configured to the estimates obtained from the empirical data (grey line)

(scenario $t2$ represented by blue lines in Figure 6c) or twice this level (scenario $t3$ represented by red lines in Figure 6c). Notably, the largest improvement is observed in the shift from scenario $t1$ to $t2$, suggesting that a rapid reaction in making resources available holds similar relevance to increases in potential capacity.

Furthermore, changes in testing levels dominate the dynamics of the incidence rate despite variations in tracing resources ($c1$, $c2$, $c3$). Although tracing close contacts also contributes to delaying and lowering the peak, its impact is much less prominent than testing, given that its capacity is one order of magnitude

smaller. Nevertheless, regardless of the scenario, the disease is not suppressed. This result highlights an important point. Even though Scenarios 2 and 3 correspond to extreme cases of resource investment, the impact on the disease dynamics is not proportional. Thus, relying solely on *TTI* for disease control might require an unrealistic level of investment, an insight obscured by the fixed fractions approach.

Additionally, the public health system can adopt targeted strategies that remove barriers impeding individuals from seeking a diagnostic test or that promote compliance with self-isolation measures to enhance the impact of *TTI*. Consequently, we evaluate the effects of increased willingness to take a test, isolate, or both while maintaining resource levels based on the empirical data. As seen in Figure 7a, these increases in willingness further delay the peak compared to double-sized testing and tracing capabilities (scenario *t3c3* denoted by the dashed line). Notably, combining the interventions produces a greater impact than the sum of their individual effects. Nevertheless, the extended delay is not accompanied by a lower peak, as resource capacity cannot cope with the increase in demand. Therefore, the public health system must tackle physical and behavioural constraints in order to ensure an effective intervention.

Another element that undermines the effectiveness of *TTI* is the occurrence of infections originating from the preclinical class. Due to limited resources, testing guidelines primarily target the symptomatic population, making it challenging to identify individuals who do not show any symptoms through testing alone. This limitation significantly raises the risk of undetected transmission. To gauge the extent of this hindrance, we repeat the simulations shown in Figure 7a (solid lines), assuming that individuals are detected before entering the preclinical stage. In a nutshell, the simulations reveal that diagnosing earlier leads to a later peak delay (compare dot-dash in lines Figure 7b against solid lines of the same colour in Figure 7a). These results imply that disregarding the preclinical phase can overstate the impact of interventions, and there is significant leverage in detecting preclinical individuals if made feasible.

Mobility restrictions

Instead of a targeted approach such as *TTI*, decision-makers can also opt for society-wide mobility restrictions to limit the movements of the entire population so that the risk of exposure to the transmissible pathogen is reduced. We model this countermeasure by reformulating the transmission rate (B_t) in the SEI3R profile (Eq. 1) as the product between the probability of infection (ν) and a time-varying contact rate (ζ_t), whose dynamics are governed by a mobility index (Z_t). This index is relative to the average number of contacts without external interventions (ζ_0). It thus follows that $Z_0 = 1$. Regarding the behaviour of Z_t , mobility data (Andrade and Duggan, 2022) indicates that individuals gradually adjust their mobility level to that desired by the intervention. We model this phenomenon using a first-order delay (Eq. 6) where Z_t^* denotes the desired mobility level set by the government and τ^Z the adjustment time.

Fig. 7. (a) Effect of changes in behaviour on the incidence rate. This plot compares the impact of alternative scenarios (coloured lines) of compliance. In particular, we vary the willingness of individuals to take a test if they have symptoms and the willingness of individuals to isolate if they receive a positive test. For comparison, we include a solid grey line that denotes the scenario obtained from midpoints of willingness estimates calculated from the empirical data and a dashed grey line that denotes the resource scenario where capacity starts at its maximum, which is twice the estimated values (scenario t3 c3). (b) Simulating the effect of diagnosing individuals at the preclinical stage on the incidence rate. The dot-dashed lines indicate levels of compliance identical to those denoted by the solid lines in (a), but it is assumed that individuals are identified immediately after becoming infectious. For comparison, the solid grey line indicates the reference TTI scenario (ref TTI)

$$\begin{aligned}
 B_t &= v\zeta_t \\
 \zeta_t &= \zeta_0 Z_t \\
 \dot{Z} &= \frac{Z_t^* - Z_t}{\tau^Z} \\
 Z_t^* &= 1 - f(\min(\xi, Q_t^m), \tau^m) \\
 \dot{Q}_t^m &= f(\min(\xi, Q_t^m), \tau^m)
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

While strict mobility restrictions may be necessary, they can also be highly disruptive, and implementing them for extended periods can be challenging (Salathé *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, in alignment with the theme of this article, we posit that Z_t^* is also subject to resource constraints. That is, following the recommendation from public health authorities, governments can decrease the mobility level only

if a budget is available (Q_t^m) to support the intervention. Here, budget refers to an abstract measure expressing the number of days the restrictions can stay active at the maximum level of stringency ($\xi = 1$). Crucially, governments can extend the intervention if the stringency is below its maximum level. In other words, the budget's draining is proportional to the stringency of the restriction. Once the budget is depleted, governments lift the restriction, and individuals gradually return to their usual contact patterns. Lastly, this structure incorporates a function f that allows the intervention to start τ^m days after the first case.

We incorporate mobility restrictions (MR) into the *TTI* model and allocate a budget based on community mitigation guidelines to prevent pandemic influenza (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2007; Qualls *et al.*, 2017). These guidelines suggest a range of 2–24 weeks, depending on the aim of the intervention. For exploratory purposes, we adopt the midpoint (12 weeks, rounded to 90 days). Figure 8a illustrates the impact of *TTI* without *MR* (dotted line) and vice versa (dashed line) on the incidence rate. Additionally, the combined effect of both measures is depicted by the red line. Similar to *TTI*, *MR* also slow the transmission process, and when combined, they produce a substantial delaying effect. This effect stems from a synergistic interaction, where mobility restrictions lessen the burden on resources, retarding the collapse of the testing and tracing rates while shortening the troughs (Figure 8b).

Although the policy of *TTI* + *MR* significantly contains the spread of the disease, this outcome occurs at the expense of stringent restrictions (80% reduction in mobility). Therefore, we explore whether variations in stringency (ξ) and the time at which the intervention starts (τ^m) can result in similar outcomes with less restrictive impositions. In particular, we run a sensitivity analysis on the *TTI* + *MR* model, where we vary ξ and τ^m . For each run, we estimate the attack rate at days 180 and 270 and plot the results in Figure 8c. This plot provides two crucial insights. First, effective containment can only be achieved with strict restrictions ($\xi > 50\%$). Second, a policy can be a success or failure, depending on the time at which it is judged. If the goal were to contain the disease up to 180 days after the first case, restrictions above 50% stringency and implemented before day 40 would yield an attack rate near zero (yellow region). Three months later, however, the success region reduces to a narrow band, and previously successfully deemed policies appear ineffective.

For academic completeness, we elaborate on the narrow band. It represents a set of decisions that, in theory, can achieve long-term reductions in the attack rate through the combined use of *TTI* and *MR*. This approach allows the population to build sufficient immunity through natural infection before suppressing case growth using *MR*. Thereafter, *TTI* effectively controls the disease due to high immunity levels, low case numbers ($\mathfrak{R}_t < 1$), and manageable resource demands. We provide the technical details in Appendix S2 (section 3.2) in the online supporting information for interested readers. To further illustrate this approach, we show a simulation (beige dashed line) in Figure 8a, where *MR* start on day 40. Noticeably, this intervention achieves the lowest peak and attack rate among the scenarios in the plot. Although this finding highlights the interplay between immunity and control strategies, it is not intended as a policy recommendation. In practice, governments cannot fine-tune parameters as precisely as within a

Fig. 8. (a) Comparing the effect of four combinations of interventions on the incidence rate: only TTI; only MR; TTI + MR, where MR start at day 0; and TTI + MR, where MR start at day 40. (b) Comparing the dynamics of the testing and tracing fractions under two interventions: TTI (grey dotted line) and TTI + MR (red solid line), where MR start at day 40. (c) Sensitivity analysis on the attack rate evaluated at 2 days: 180 and 270. We vary the stringency and the time at which mobility restrictions start. TTI: Testing, tracing, and isolation. MR, mobility restrictions

simulation model. Additionally, relying on natural infection for herd immunity is undesirable. A portion of these infections will result in hospitalisations and deaths, as well as a potential risk of long-term effects of disease and comorbidity, and immunity may wane in the long run.

Vaccination

As discussed previously, immunity plays a critical role in disease dynamics. In the absence of external interventions ($\epsilon_t = 1$ in Eq. 3), disease transmission subsides only when a population reaches sufficient immunity levels. From a mathematical perspective, this decline commences when the proportion of immune individuals ($1 - s_t$) crosses a critical value known as the *herd immunity threshold* ($1 - \frac{1}{R_0}$) (Vynnycky and White, 2010). The public health system can reach safely high immunity levels by employing one of the most important inventions in the

history of science: vaccines (Plotkin, 2014). We model this intervention (V) by adding a transition between the susceptible state (S_t) and the recovered state (R_t), bypassing the infection paths (Figure 9). See equations in Appendix S3 in the online supporting information.

The time-varying vaccination fraction governs the flow of the transition $S_t \rightarrow R_t$. Considering that immunisation campaigns require an adequate and consistent vaccine supply and a robust healthcare infrastructure (vaccination centres, trained personnel, and cold chain storage facilities), we formulate this fraction as the minimum between vaccination demand and vaccination capacity normalised by the number of susceptible individuals. Formally, vaccination capacity is represented by a function that accounts for vaccine availability. In this case, we assume a pandemic vaccine becomes available 6 months after the first case (Qualls *et al.*, 2017). Once vaccines are made available, vaccination capacity follows the dynamics of the logistic structure. We leverage the Dutch open data (RIVM, 2021) to estimate the potential level of vaccination resources in the event of a pandemic (see Appendix S3 in the online supporting information for the complete details). This data indicates that the Dutch health system could initially vaccinate 300,000 people per week. Over 6 weeks, this capacity can be scaled up to 1,500,000 people per week. We refer to this scenario as the reference scenario ($C1$). It is important to note that these estimates only consider health infrastructure and assume sufficient vaccine supply.

Moreover, since not every individual who receives a vaccine acquires immunity against infection (Bubar *et al.*, 2021), we incorporate a measure of vaccine effectiveness (Fleming *et al.*, 2010). It then follows that a fraction of individuals remain susceptible after vaccination (S_t^v). Additionally, immunisation campaigns must deal with a segment of the population (S_t^h) that refuses the intervention (*vaccine hesitancy*) despite the availability of vaccination services (MacDonald, 2015). Estimates for vaccine effectiveness are derived from existing literature (Fleming *et al.*, 2010), while data collected during the COVID-19 pandemic (RIVM Corona Behavioural Unit, 2021) provide a plausible estimate for vaccination willingness ($i^v = 0.75$). We use the latter to set the initial values of the stocks S_t and S_t^h . The resulting structure (Figure 10) allows testing the aggregate impact of a comprehensive intervention (Halloran *et al.*, 2008), comprising TTI , MR , and V . We configure this model to the resource estimates obtained from Dutch open data. As expected, adding vaccination to the response provides additional benefits, resulting in a lower peak (Figure 11a) and a long-term decrease in the number of cumulative infections (Figure 11b). In particular, this model predicts that a $TTI + MR + V$ intervention prevents 5 million people from acquiring the disease.

Despite the countermeasures reducing the attack rate, the model predicts that nearly 12 million people in the Netherlands (67% of the 17.5 million population) will contract the disease within a year, even with comprehensive interventions in place. This high infection level occurs because of competition between natural infection (solid blue line Figure 11b) and vaccination for susceptible individuals. The dotted line in Figure 11b indicates the percentage of people effectively vaccinated over time. Even though the vaccination campaign starts before lifting the

Fig. 9. Vaccine structure. (Sh, hesitant susceptible; Sv, vaccinated who remain susceptible)

Fig. 10. Stock-and-flow diagram of a response that combines four countermeasures: vaccination, testing and isolation, contact tracing, and mobility restrictions. (Shq, hesitant susceptible in quarantine)

mobility restrictions, its pace is limited due to resource constraints to the extent that natural infections eventually overwhelm the vaccination effort.

As with previous countermeasures, we explore how changes in vaccination constraints impact the dynamics of the disease. For physical constraints, we propose an additional scenario (*C2*) in which vaccination resources start at maximum capacity. Regarding behavioural constraints, we test the consequences of vaccine misinformation by decreasing the willingness to vaccinate. We combine these scenarios into four simulations. Intuitively, if capacity is limited (*C1*), variations in willingness become inconsequential, as shown by the solid lines in Figure 11c. Conversely, when vaccination capacity can meet the demand (dotted lines), willingness plays a crucial role in the containment of the disease. Observe

Fig. 11. (a) Comparing the effect of three combinations of interventions on the incidence rate: no-intervention (base case); nonpharmaceutical (TTI + MR); comprehensive (TTI + MR + V). (b) Comparing the effect of three combinations of interventions on the attack rate: no-intervention (base case), nonpharmaceutical (TTI + MR), and comprehensive (TTI + MR + V). We also include the percentage of immune population due to vaccination. (c) Simulation of the comprehensive intervention (illustrated by the attack rate) under four scenarios, where we combine two levels of vaccination capacity (denoted by the line type) with two levels of vaccination willingness (denoted by the colour of the lines)

the disparity between the blue and the grey dotted lines. The blue dotted line represents the only scenario in this study that maintains the attack rate below 25% in the long term. In essence, successfully containing a pandemic of this nature demands a comprehensive approach, high vaccination willingness, and swift reactions to employ potential capacity.

Conclusions

Although no one can predict the timing and nature of the next pandemic, the extent of its potential impact will depend on the ability of public health systems, healthcare services, and governments to respond. This response, in turn, relies on the level of resources available for immediate use. Therefore, any model aiming to provide a realistic assessment of the effect of countermeasures must incorporate structures that reflect resource constraints. Given the scarcity of readily available estimates of resource capacity, modellers have represented resource capacity

as a fixed fraction of resource demand. However, as demonstrated by the *TTI* example, this strategy can predict overly optimistic outcomes during periods of high resource demand. This inaccuracy occurs because, irrespective of the specific fraction, it is implicitly and unrealistically assumed that the dynamics of resources will follow those of infections. Furthermore, representing policies as fractions may create the illusion that the intensity of a policy is a decision rather than a consequence of available resources.

On the contrary, when resources are represented by a more realistic structure, such as the logistic growth formulation, the *TTI* model predicts a less favourable outcome: a temporary containment of the disease but a long-term attack rate similar to that of a no-intervention scenario. This containment occurs during the early stage of the pandemic and lasts until the demand for resources overwhelms their capacity. Similarly, incorporating mobility restrictions (*TTI + MR*) merely extends the temporary containment but does not lead to sustained reductions in infection levels. Instead, only a comprehensive intervention (*TTI + MR + V*) substantially mitigates the impact of an influenza pandemic in the short and long run.

While a comprehensive intervention reduces the long-term attack rate, the simulation still suggests that a noticeable fraction of the population will be infected. To further improve these results, the public health system can employ the strategies explored during the scenario analysis accompanying the discussion of each countermeasure. These strategies comprise increases in the level of resources, quicker reactions to harness potential capacity, and the introduction of behavioural interventions. Although this work demonstrates how to explore the effects of improvement proposals, it cannot provide prescriptive guidance, as each strategy involves different types of investment and costs. We illustrate this point using testing capacity. In this context, increasing potential capacity means expanding the network of diagnostic laboratories (new facilities), whereas a swifter reaction implies boosting laboratory throughput for the specific pathogen. Moreover, behavioural interventions involve campaigns that increase testing demand. Prioritising the effort allocated to each strategy depends on a cost–benefit analysis, for which we lack access to estimates. This information would enable an exhaustive assessment of interventions, including budgetary considerations, where investments in one intervention reduce the budget available for others. Naturally, further work addressing this topic is recommended.

Admittedly, our simulations are based on structures calibrated through a rudimentary optimisation procedure. Despite this difficulty, the fitted structure (logistic model) appears to reproduce the underlying dynamics of capacity growth. It should be noted that the conclusions from this study do not hinge upon precise estimates. Nevertheless, it would be beneficial for preparedness plans to include centralised procedures within countries that allow for accurate and real-time estimation of the potential capacity of each intervention in the event of a pandemic.

Furthermore, portraying a pandemic's state requires considering multiple indicators. We focused on cases (incidence and attack rates) as the primary metric, assuming a proportional relationship with other factors such as hospitalisations and deaths. However, this approach may overlook the full impact of interventions. For example, interventions (e.g., *TTI*) that *flatten the curve* – reducing the incidence peak – can significantly lessen the burden on healthcare systems by staggering the cases and potentially prevent additional deaths, even if the overall

case count remains the same. Interestingly, our simulations indicate that reducing the peak is only possible with increased resources (see [Testing and isolation](#)). Additionally, we simplified the impact of vaccination by focusing primarily on its ability to prevent infection. This assumption may not be entirely realistic as a vaccine may not effectively prevent illness, but it can still demonstrate significant effectiveness in preventing death, rendering a mortality indicator more appropriate. This change of indicator, though, would not negate the need for well-resourced vaccination efforts.

For simplicity, we also omitted certain realistic features. The choice of a deterministic model precludes disease extinction when the number of infected people is small (e.g., due to stringent mobility restrictions)—an aspect realistically captured by models with demographic and environmental stochasticity. We allowed the model to produce outbreaks even when the number of infected people is infinitesimal, envisioning it as the risk of an imported case. Even though further improvements could explicitly incorporate travel-related effects, this decision entails the potential drawback of introducing an unmanageable number of parameters to be configured.

Additionally, we assumed that infection and vaccination confer perfect immunity. However, empirical studies (Barry *et al.*, 2008; Matthes *et al.*, 2023) have demonstrated that while prior illness affords protection against subsequent pandemic influenza infections, this immunity wanes over time, leading to reinfections during later waves. Consequently, the applicability of the model presented in this paper is confined to relatively short and medium time frames, where the emergence of new variants does not play a predominant role in immunity escape. However, this limitation does not compromise the utility of this model, given that the largest proportion of adverse effects typically occurs during the initial stages of a pandemic. For example, most deaths from the 1918 influenza pandemic occurred during its second wave, a three-month period from mid-September to mid-December of 1918 (Barry, 2004).

Other simplifications adopted in this paper concern the aggregation of age and spatial-related effects and the exclusion of a balancing feedback mechanism between the state of a pandemic and individual behaviour (e.g., number of contacts, use of personal protective equipment). Including these realistic features could reveal a more nuanced picture of the assessed interventions and offer more accurate predictions. Nonetheless, these enhancements will not compensate for omissions in formulating a realistic resource structure.

Therefore, this work not only provides a more plausible representation of pandemic management but also emphasises the importance of building the necessary resources to respond to pandemics. While it may be tempting to attribute the success or failure of pandemic management solely to decisions made in the response phase, the fate of millions of people may already be determined by the choices made during the preparedness phase.

Acknowledgements

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 883285. The

material presented and views expressed here are the responsibility of the author (s) only. The EU Commission takes no responsibility for any use made of the information set out. The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript. Open access funding provided by IReL.

Biographies

Jair Andrade is a research associate at the University of Galway. His research focuses on statistical inference and model simulation to study infectious disease dynamics.

Berend Beishuizen is a researcher at the Centre for Infectious Disease Control at the Dutch National Institute for Public Health and the Environment, and a PhD candidate at the Radboudumc in Nijmegen, the Netherlands. His research is focused on identifying gaps in the resource management aspect of pandemic preparedness and antimicrobial resistance.

Mart Stein is an infectious disease epidemiologist and research coordinator at the LCI of the Centre for Infectious Disease Control at the Dutch National Institute for Public Health and the Environment, the Netherlands. His research focuses on pandemic preparedness and response.

Máire Connolly is an Established Professor of Global and Environmental Public Health at the University of Galway. Her research interests include the application of modelling to support decision-making in outbreak response and pandemic preparedness training. She is a member of the Modelling Advisory Group to the Health Protection Surveillance Centre (HPSC) in Ireland and WHO's Global Outbreak and Response Network (GOARN).

Jim Duggan is a Personal Professor in Computer Science at the University of Galway, and his research interests center on the application of system dynamics modelling and data science to enhance public health policy. He has recently applied system dynamics modelling with the Irish Epidemiological Modelling Advisory Group (IEMAG), where his role is to work as part of a team to develop and deliver epidemiological models to inform operational and policy decision-making. Jim is a Managing Editor of the System Dynamics Review and is a member of the World Health Organisation's Global Outbreak Alert and Response Network (GOARN).

References

- Allen LJS. 2017. A primer on stochastic epidemic models: formulation, numerical simulation, and analysis. *Infectious Disease Modelling* **2**: 128–142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.idm.2017.03.001>.
- Anderson RM, May RM. 1992. *Infectious diseases of humans: dynamics and control*. Oxford University Press: New York.
- Andrade J, Duggan J. 2020. An evaluation of Hamiltonian Monte Carlo performance to calibrate age-structured compartmental SEIR models to incidence data. *Epidemics* **33**: 100415. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epidem.2020.100415>.
- Andrade J, Duggan J. 2021. A Bayesian approach to calibrate system dynamics models using Hamiltonian Monte Carlo. *System Dynamics Review* **37**: 283–309. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sdr.1693>.
- Andrade J, Duggan J. 2022. Inferring the effective reproductive number from deterministic and semi-deterministic compartmental models using incidence and mobility data. *PLoS Computational Biology* **18**: 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1010206>.
- Andrade J, Duggan J. 2023. Anchoring the mean generation time in the SEIR to mitigate biases in \mathcal{R}_0 estimates due to uncertainty in the distribution of the epidemiological delays. *Royal Society Open Science* **10**: 230515. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.230515>.
- Auping WL, Pruyt E, Kwakkel JH. 2017. Simulating endogenous dynamics of intervention-capacity deployment: Ebola outbreak in Liberia. *International Journal of Systems Science: Operations & Logistics* **4**: 53–67. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23302674.2015.1128576>.
- Bacaër N. 2011. Verhulst and the Logistic Equation (1838). In *A Short History of Mathematical Population Dynamics*. Springer London: London; 35–39. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-85729-115-8_6.
- Barlas Y. 1996. Formal aspects of model validity and validation in system dynamics. *System Dynamics Review* **12**: 183–210. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1099-1727\(199623\)12:3%3C183::AID-SDR103%3E3.0.CO;2-4](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1099-1727(199623)12:3%3C183::AID-SDR103%3E3.0.CO;2-4).
- Barney J. 1991. Firm resources and sustained competitive advantage. *Journal of Management* **17**: 99–120. <https://doi.org/10.1177/014920639101700108>.
- Barry JM. 2004. The site of origin of the 1918 influenza pandemic and its public health implications. *Journal of Translational Medicine* **2**: 3. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1479-5876-2-3>.
- Barry JM, Viboud C, Simonsen L. 2008. Cross-protection between successive waves of the 1918–1919 influenza pandemic: epidemiological evidence from US army camps and from Britain. *The Journal of Infectious Diseases* **198**: 1427–1434. <https://doi.org/10.1086/592454>.
- Brett T, Ajelli M, Liu Q-H, Krauland MG, Grefenstette JJ, van Panhuis WG, Vespignani A, Drake JM, Rohani P. 2020. Detecting critical slowing down in high-dimensional epidemiological systems. *PLoS Computational Biology* **16**: 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1007679>.
- Brouwer AF. 2022. Why the spectral radius? An intuition-building introduction to the basic reproduction number. *Bulletin of Mathematical Biology* **84**: 96. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11538-022-01057-9>.
- Bubar KM, Reinholt K, Kissler SM, Lipsitch M, Cobey S, Grad YH, Larremore DB. 2021. Model-informed COVID-19 vaccine prioritization strategies by age and serostatus. *Science* **371**: 916–921. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abe6959>.
- Bushman M, Kahn R, Taylor BP, Lipsitch M, Hanage WP. 2021. Population impact of SARS-CoV-2 variants with enhanced transmissibility and/or partial immune escape. *Cell* **184**: 6229–6242.e18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2021.11.026>.

- Camacho A, Kucharski AJ, Funk S, Breman J, Piot P, Edmunds WJ. 2014. Potential for large outbreaks of ebola virus disease. *Epidemics* **9**: 70–78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epidem.2014.09.003>.
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention 2007. Interim pre-pandemic planning guidance: Community strategy for pandemic influenza mitigation in the united states: Early, targeted, layered use of nonpharmaceutical interventions. <https://stacks.cdc.gov/view/cdc/11425>.
- Chowell G, Ammon CE, Hengartner NW, Hyman JM. 2006. Transmission dynamics of the great influenza pandemic of 1918 in Geneva, Switzerland: assessing the effects of hypothetical interventions. *Journal of Theoretical Biology* **241**: 193–204. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtbi.2005.11.026>.
- Chowell G, Nishiura H, Bettencourt LMA. 2007. Comparative estimation of the reproduction number for pandemic influenza from daily case notification data. *Journal of the Royal Society Interface* **4**: 155–166. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsif.2006.0161>.
- Daems R, Del Giudice G, Rappuoli R. 2005. Anticipating crisis: towards a pandemic flu vaccination strategy through alignment of public health and industrial policy. *Vaccine* **23**: 5732–5742. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2005.10.011>.
- Davies N, Klepac P, Liu Y, Prem K, Jit M, Pearson CAB, Quilty BJ, Kucharski AJ, Gibbs H, Clifford S, Gimma A, van Zandvoort K, Munday JD, Diamond C, Edmunds WJ, Houben RMGJ, Hellewell J, Russell TW, Abbott S, Funk S, Bosse NI, Sun YF, Flasche S, Rosello A, Jarvis CI, Eggo RM, CMMID COVID-19 working group. 2020a. Age-dependent effects in the transmission and control of COVID-19 epidemics. *Nature Medicine* **26**: 1205–1211. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-020-0962-9>.
- Davies N, Kucharski A, Eggo R, Gimma A, Edmunds J, Jombart T, O'Reilly K, Endo A, Hellewell J, Nightingale E, Quilty B, Jarvis C, Russell T, Klepac P, Bosse N, Funk S, Abbott S, Medley G, Gibbs H, Pearson C, Flasche S, Jit M, Clifford S, Prem K, Diamond C, Emery J, Deol A, Procter S, van Zandvoort K, Sun Y, Munday J, Rosello A, Auzenbergs M, Knight G, Houben R, Liu Y. 2020b. Effects of non-pharmaceutical interventions on COVID-19 cases, deaths, and demand for hospital services in the UK: a modelling study. *The Lancet Public Health* **5**: e375–e385. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2468-2667\(20\)30133-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2468-2667(20)30133-X).
- Di Domenico L, Pullano G, Sabbatini CE, Boëlle P-Y, Colizza V. 2020. Impact of lockdown on COVID-19 epidemic in Île-de-France and possible exit strategies. *BMC Medicine* **18**: 240. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12916-020-01698-4>.
- Diekmann O, Heesterbeek JAP, Metz JAJ. 1990. On the definition and the computation of the basic reproduction ratio R_0 in models for infectious diseases in heterogeneous populations. *Journal of Mathematical Biology* **28**: 365–382. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00178324>.
- Douglas M, Katikireddi SV, Taulbut M, McKee M, McCartney G. 2020. Mitigating the wider health effects of covid-19 pandemic response. *BMJ* **369**: m1557. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.m1557>.
- Duggan J, Andrade J, Murphy TB, Gleeson JP, Walsh C, Nolan P. 2024. An age-cohort simulation model for generating COVID-19 scenarios: a study from Ireland's pandemic response. *European Journal of Operational Research* **313**: 343–358. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2023.08.011>.
- Duintjer Tebbens RJ, Pallansch MA, Kew OM, Cáceres VM, Sutter RW, Thompson KM. 2005. A dynamic model of poliomyelitis outbreaks: learning from the past to help inform the future. *American Journal of Epidemiology* **162**: 358–372. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aje/kwi206>.
- Eames KT, Webb C, Thomas K, Smith J, Salmon R, Temple JMF. 2010. Assessing the role of contact tracing in a suspected H7N2 influenza outbreak in humans in Wales. *BMC Infectious Diseases* **10**: 141. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2334-10-141>.

- Eames KTD, Keeling MJ. 2003. Contact tracing and disease control. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London Series B: Biological Sciences* **270**: 2565–2571. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2003.2554>.
- Epstein JM, Hatna E, Crodelle J. 2021. Triple contagion: a two-fears epidemic model. *Journal of the Royal Society Interface* **18**: 20210186. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsif.2021.0186>.
- Flahault A, Vergu E, Coudeville L, Grais RF. 2006. Strategies for containing a global influenza pandemic. *Vaccine* **24**: 6751–6755. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2006.05.079>.
- Fleming DM, Andrews NJ, Ellis JS, Bermingham A, Sebastianpillai P, Elliot AJ, Miller E, Zambon M. 2010. Estimating influenza vaccine effectiveness using routinely collected laboratory data. *Journal of Epidemiology & Community Health* **64**: 1062–1067. <https://doi.org/10.1136/jech.2009.093450>.
- Fong M, Gao H, Wong J, Xiao J, Shiu EYC, Ryu S, Cowling B. 2020. Nonpharmaceutical measures for pandemic influenza in nonhealthcare settings—social distancing measures. *Emerging Infectious Disease Journal* **26**: 976. <https://doi.org/10.3201/eid2605.190995>.
- Fraser C, Riley S, Anderson RM, Ferguson NM. 2004. Factors that make an infectious disease outbreak controllable. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **101**: 6146–6151. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0307506101>.
- Gessain A, Nakoune E, Yazdanpanah Y. 2022. Monkeypox. *New England Journal of Medicine* **387**: 1783–1793. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMr2208860>.
- GGD 2020. Doorontwikkelen en vernellen BCO capaciteit. https://www.eerstekamer.nl/bijlage/20200828/bijlage_a_doorontwikkelen_en/document3/f=/vbluccu5mbz.pdf [accessed 8th December 2023].
- Ghaffarzadegan N, Lyneis J, Richardson GP. 2011. How small system dynamics models can help the public policy process. *System Dynamics Review* **27**: 22–44. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sdr.442>.
- Ghaffarzadegan N, Mostafavi S, Kim H. 2023. Sociotechnical interdependencies and tipping-point dynamics in data-intensive services. *System Dynamics Review* **39**: 5–31. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sdr.1724>.
- Gleeson JP, Brendan Murphy T, O'Brien JD, Friel N, Bargary N, O'Sullivan DJP. 2022. Calibrating COVID-19 susceptible-exposed-infected-removed models with time-varying effective contact rates. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences* **380**: 20210120. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2021.0120>.
- Gostic KM, McGough L, Baskerville EB, Abbott S, Joshi K, Tedijanto C, Kahn R, Niehus R, Hay JA, De Salazar PM, Hellewell J, Meakin S, Munday JD, Bosse NI, Sherrat K, Thompson RN, White LF, Huisman JS, Scire J, Bonhoeffer S, Stadler T, Wallinga J, Funk S, Lipsitch M, Cobey S. 2020. Practical considerations for measuring the effective reproductive number, Rt. *PLoS Computational Biology* **16**: e1008409. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1008409>.
- Gu Y, Komiya N, Kamiya H, Yasui Y, Taniguchi K, Okabe N. 2011. Pandemic (H1N1) 2009 transmission during presymptomatic phase, Japan. *Emerging Infectious Disease journal* **17**: 1737. <https://doi.org/10.3201/eid1709.101411>.
- Halloran ME, Ferguson NM, Eubank S, Longini IM, Cummings DAT, Lewis B, Xu S, Fraser C, Vullikanti A, Germann TC, Wagener D, Beckman R, Kadau K, Barrett C, Macken CA, Burke DS, Cooley P. 2008. Modeling targeted layered containment of an influenza pandemic in the United States. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **105**: 4639–4644. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0706849105>.
- Heesterbeek JAP, Dietz K. 1996. The concept of ro in epidemic theory. *Statistica Neerlandica* **50**: 89–110. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9574.1996.tb01482.x>.
- Heffernan JM, Smith RJ, Wahl LM. 2005. Perspectives on the basic reproductive ratio. *Journal of the Royal Society Interface* **2**: 281–293. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsif.2005.0042>.

- Hollingsworth TD, Klinkenberg D, Heesterbeek H, Anderson RM. 2011. Mitigation strategies for pandemic influenza a: Balancing conflicting policy objectives. *PLoS Computational Biology* **7**: 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1001076>.
- Homer JB. 1996. Why we iterate: scientific modeling in theory and practice. *System Dynamics Review* **12**: 1–19. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1099-1727\(199621\)12:1%3C1::AID-SDR93%3E3.0.CO;2-P](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1099-1727(199621)12:1%3C1::AID-SDR93%3E3.0.CO;2-P).
- Homer JB. 2012. Partial-model testing as a validation tool for system dynamics (1983). *System Dynamics Review* **28**: 281–294. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sdr.1478>.
- House T, Ross JV, Sirl D. 2013. How big is an outbreak likely to be? Methods for epidemic final-size calculation. *Proceedings of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences* **469**: 20120436. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspa.2012.0436>.
- Howard J, Huang A, Li Z, Tufekci Z, Zdimar V, van der Westhuizen H-M, von Delft A, Price A, Fridman L, Tang L-H, Tang V, Watson GL, Bax CE, Shaikh R, Questier F, Hernandez D, Chu LF, Ramirez CM, Rimoin AW. 2021. An evidence review of face masks against COVID-19. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **118**: e2014564118. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2014564118>.
- isee Systems. 2022. *Stella Architect*. isee Systems: Lebanon, NH.
- Keeling MJ, Grenfell BT. 2002. Understanding the persistence of measles: reconciling theory, simulation and observation. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London Series B: Biological Sciences* **269**: 335–343. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2001.1898>.
- Keeling MJ, Rohani P. 2008. *Modeling infectious diseases in humans and animals*. Princeton University Press: Princeton.
- Krumkamp R, Kretzschmar M, Rudge JW, Ahmad A, Aanvoravongchai P, Westenhoefer J, Stein M, Putthasri W, Coker R. 2011. Health service resource needs for pandemic influenza in developing countries: a linked transmission dynamics, interventions and resource demand model. *Epidemiology & Infection* **139**: 59–67. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0950268810002220>.
- Krylova O, Earn DJD. 2013. Effects of the infectious period distribution on predicted transitions in childhood disease dynamics. *Journal of the Royal Society Interface* **10**: 20130098. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsif.2013.0098>.
- Lane DC. 1992. Modelling as learning: A consultancy methodology for enhancing learning in management teams. *European Journal of Operational Research* **59**: 64–84. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0377-2217\(92\)90007-V](https://doi.org/10.1016/0377-2217(92)90007-V).
- Lee J-W, McKibbin WJ. 2004. Globalization and disease: the case of SARS. *Asian Economic Papers* **3**: 113–131. <https://doi.org/10.1162/1535351041747932>.
- Leung NHL, Xu C, Ip DKM, Cowling BJ. 2015. Review article: the fraction of influenza virus infections that are asymptomatic. *Epidemiology* **26**: 862–872. <https://doi.org/10.1097/EDE.0000000000000340>.
- Lloyd AL. 2001. Realistic distributions of infectious periods in epidemic models: changing patterns of persistence and dynamics. *Theoretical Population Biology* **60**: 59–71. <https://doi.org/10.1006/tpbi.2001.1525>.
- MacDonald NE. 2015. Vaccine hesitancy: Definition, scope and determinants. *Vaccine* **33**: 4161–4164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2015.04.036>.
- Marani M, Katul GG, Pan WK, Parolari AJ. 2021. Intensity and frequency of extreme novel epidemics. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **118**: e2105482118. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2105482118>.
- Matthes KL, Le Vu M, Bhattacharyya U, Galliker A, Kordi M, Floris J, Staub K. 2023. Reinfections and cross-protection in the 1918/19 influenza pandemic: revisiting a survey among male and female factory workers. *International Journal of Public Health* **68**: 1605777. <https://doi.org/10.3389/ijph.2023.1605777>.
- Mills CE, Robins JM, Lipsitch M. 2004. Transmissibility of 1918 pandemic influenza. *Nature* **432**: 904–906. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature03063>.

- Monto AS. 2003. The role of antivirals in the control of influenza. *Vaccine* **21**: 1796–1800. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0264-410X\(03\)00075-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0264-410X(03)00075-6).
- Monto AS, Fukuda K. 2019. Lessons from influenza pandemics of the last 100 years. *Clinical Infectious Diseases* **70**: 951–957. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/ciz803>.
- Monto AS, Webster RG. 2013. Influenza pandemics: history and lessons learned. In *Textbook of Influenza*. Wiley-Blackwell: Hoboken, New Jersey; 20–34. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118636817.ch2>.
- Morens DM, Folkers GK, Fauci AS. 2009. What is a pandemic? *The Journal of Infectious Diseases* **200**: 1018–1021.
- Mossong J, Nokes DJ, Edmunds WJ, Cox MJ, Ratnam S, Muller CP. 1999. Modeling the impact of subclinical measles transmission in vaccinated populations with waning immunity. *American Journal of Epidemiology* **150**: 1238–1249. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordjournals.aje.a009951>.
- Nishiura H, Chowell G. 2009. The effective reproduction number as a prelude to statistical estimation of time-dependent epidemic trends. In *Mathematical and Statistical Estimation Approaches in Epidemiology*, Chowell G, Hyman JM, Bettencourt LMA, Castillo-Chavez C (eds). Springer: Netherlands, Dordrecht; 103–121. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-90-481-2313-1_5.
- Park SW, Bolker BM. 2020. A note on observation processes in epidemic models. *Bulletin of Mathematical Biology* **82**: 37. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11538-020-00713-2>.
- Peteraf MA. 1993. The cornerstones of competitive advantage: a resource-based view. *Strategic Management Journal* **14**: 179–191.
- Plotkin S. 2014. History of vaccination. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **111**: 12283–12287. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1400472111>.
- Qualls N, Levitt CA, Kanade N, Wright-Jegede N, Dopson S, Biggerstaff M, Reed C, Uzicanin A. 2017. Community mitigation guidelines to prevent pandemic influenza — United States, 2017: Technical report 1: Chapters 1–4. Atlanta, GA.
- R Core Team. 2023. *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. R Foundation for Statistical Computing: Vienna, Austria.
- Rahmandad H. 2022. Behavioral responses to risk promote vaccinating high-contact individuals first. *System Dynamics Review* **38**: 246–263. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sdr.1714>.
- Rahmandad H, Lim TY, Sterman J. 2021. Behavioral dynamics of COVID-19: estimating underreporting, multiple waves, and adherence fatigue across 92 nations. *System Dynamics Review* **37**: 5–31. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sdr.1673>.
- Rahmandad H, Xu R, Ghaffarzadegan N. 2022. A missing behavioural feedback in COVID-19 models is the key to several puzzles. *BMJ Global Health* **7**: e010463. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2022-010463>.
- Rashid H, Ridda I, King C, Begun M, Tekin H, Wood JG, Booy R. 2015. Evidence compendium and advice on social distancing and other related measures for response to an influenza pandemic. *Paediatric Respiratory Reviews* **16**: 119–126. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prrv.2014.01.003>.
- Renshaw E. 1993. *Modelling Biological Populations in Space and Time (Cambridge Studies in Mathematical Biology)*. Cambridge University Press: Cambridge, UK.
- RIVM. 2021. Uitvoering vaccinatiestrategie COVID-19. https://www.medicalfacts.nl/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Presentatie_de_heer_Jaap_van_Delden_programmadirecteur_vaccinatie_COVID-19_bij_het_RIVM1.pdf [accessed 8th November 2023].
- RIVM Corona Behavioural Unit. 2021. Expressions of doubt and concern in relation to COVID-19 vaccination: a mixed methodological approach. <https://www.rivm.nl/documenten/expressions-of-doubt-and-concern-in-relation-to-covid-19-vaccination-mixed> [accessed 12th June 2023].
- Ryu S, Gao H, Wong J, Shiu EYC, Xiao J, Fong MW, Cowling B. 2020. Nonpharmaceutical measures for pandemic influenza in nonhealthcare settings—international travel-related

- measures. *Emerging Infectious Disease Journal* **26**: 961. <https://doi.org/10.3201/eid2605.190993>.
- Salathé M, Althaus CL, Neher R, Stringhini S, Hodcroft E, Fellay J, Zwahlen M, Senti G, Battegay M, Wilder-Smith A, Eckerle I, Egger M, Low N. 2020. COVID-19 epidemic in Switzerland: on the importance of testing, contact tracing and isolation. *Swiss Medical Weekly* **150**: w20225. <https://doi.org/10.4414/smww.2020.20225>.
- Shrestha SS, Swerdlow DL, Borse RH, Prabhu VS, Finelli L, Atkins CY, Owusu-Edusei K, Bell B, Mead PS, Biggerstaff M, Brammer L, Davidson H, Jernigan D, Jhung MA, Kamimoto LA, Merlin TL, Nowell M, Redd SC, Reed C, Schuchat A, Meltzer MI. 2011. Estimating the burden of 2009 pandemic influenza A (H1N1) in the United States (April 2009–April 2010). *Clinical Infectious Diseases* **52**: S75–S82. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/ciq012>.
- Shultz JM, Baingana F, Neria Y. 2015. The 2014 Ebola outbreak and mental health: current status and recommended response. *JAMA* **313**: 567. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2014.17934>.
- Stein ML, Rudge JW, Coker R, van der Weijden C, Krumkamp R, Hanvoravongchai P, Chavez I, Putthasri W, Phommasack B, Adisasmito W, Touch S, Sat LM, Hsu Y-C, Kretzschmar M, Timen A. 2012. Development of a resource modelling tool to support decision makers in pandemic influenza preparedness: the AsiaFluCap simulator. *BMC Public Health* **12**: 870. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-12-870>.
- Sterman J. 2000. *Business dynamics: systems thinking and modeling for a complex world*. McGraw-Hill Higher Education, Irwin/McGraw-Hill: Boston.
- Strogatz S. 2018. *Nonlinear dynamics and chaos: with applications to physics, biology, chemistry, and engineering*, 2nd ed. A Chapman & Hall book and CRC Press Taylor & Francis Group: Boca Raton, FL and New York, NY.
- Sturniolo S, Waites W, Colbourn T, Manheim D, Panovska-Griffiths J. 2021. Testing, tracing and isolation in compartmental models. *PLoS Computational Biology* **17**: e1008633. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1008633>.
- Teslya M, Pham TM, Godijk NG, Kretzschmar ME, Bootsma MCJ, Rozhnova G. 2020. Impact of self-imposed prevention measures and short-term government-imposed social distancing on mitigating and delaying a COVID-19 epidemic: a modelling study. *PLoS Medicine* **17**: e1003166. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1003166>.
- Thomas Craig KJ, Rizvi R, Willis VC, Kassler WJ, Jackson GP. 2021. Effectiveness of contact tracing for viral disease mitigation and suppression: evidence-based review. *JMIR Public Health and Surveillance* **7**: e32468. <https://doi.org/10.2196/32468>.
- Thompson RN, Gilligan CA, Cunniffe NJ. 2016. Detecting presymptomatic infection is necessary to forecast major epidemics in the earliest stages of infectious disease outbreaks. *PLoS Computational Biology* **12**: 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1004836>.
- Thompson RN, Stockwin JE, van Gaalen RD, Polonsky JA, Kamvar ZN, Demarsh PA, Dahlgvist E, Li S, Miguel E, Jombart T, Lessler J, Cauchemez S, Cori A. 2019. Improved inference of time-varying reproduction numbers during infectious disease outbreaks. *Epidemics* **29**: 100356. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epidem.2019.100356>.
- van den Driessche P. 2017. Reproduction numbers of infectious disease models. *Infectious Disease Modelling* **2**: 288–303. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.idm.2017.06.002>.
- VWS 2023a. Coronavirus dashboard. <https://coronadashboard.government.nl/landelijk/gedrag> [accessed 8th November 2023].
- VWS 2023b. Dienst testen. <https://www.diensttesten.nl/over-dienst-testen/historie-van-dienst-testen> [accessed 7th June 2023].
- Vynnycky E, Edmunds WJ. 2008. Analyses of the 1957 (Asian) influenza pandemic in the United Kingdom and the impact of school closures. *Epidemiology and Infection* **136**: 166–179. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0950268807008369>.

- Vynnycky E, White RG. 2010. *An introduction to infectious disease modelling*. Oxford University Press: New York, NY.
- Wallinga J, Lipsitch M. 2007. How generation intervals shape the relationship between growth rates and reproductive numbers. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* **274**: 599–604. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2006.3754>.
- Wang H, Paulson KR, Pease SA, Watson S, Comfort H, Zheng P, Aravkin AY, Bisignano C, Barber RM, Alam T, Fuller JE, May EA, Jones DP, Frisch ME, Abbafati C, Adolph C, Allorant A, Amlag JO, Bang-Jensen B, Bertolacci GJ, Bloom SS, Carter A, Castro E, Chakrabarti S, Chattopadhyay J, Cogen RM, Collins JK, Cooperrider K, Dai X, Dangel WJ, Daoud F, Dapper C, Deen A, Duncan BB, Erickson M, Ewald SB, Fedosseeva T, Ferrari AJ, Frostad JJ, Fullman N, Gallagher J, Gamkrelidze A, Guo G, He J, Helak M, Henry NJ, Hulland EN, Huntley BM, Kereselidze M, Lazzar-Atwood A, LeGrand KE, Lindstrom A, Linebarger E, Lotufo PA, Lozano R, Magistro B, Malta DC, Månsson J, Mantilla Herrera AM, Marinho F, Mirkuzie AH, Misganaw AT, Monasta L, Naik P, Nomura S, O'Brien EG, O'Halloran JK, Olana LT, Ostroff SM, Penberthy L, Reiner RC Jr, Reinke G, Ribeiro ALP, Santomauro DF, Schmidt MI, Shaw DH, Sheena BS, Sholokhov A, Skhvtaridze N, Sorensen RJD, Spurlock EE, Syailendrawati R, Topor-Madry R, Troeger CE, Walcott R, Walker A, Wiysonge CS, Worku NA, Zigler B, Pigott DM, Naghavi M, Mokdad AH, Lim SS, Hay SI, Gakidou E, Murray CJL. 2022. Estimating excess mortality due to the COVID-19 pandemic: a systematic analysis of COVID-19-related mortality, 2020–21. *Lancet* **399**: 1513–1536. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(21\)02796-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(21)02796-3).
- World Health Organization. 2017. *Pandemic influenza risk management: a WHO guide to inform and harmonize national and international pandemic preparedness and response (technical documents)*. World Health Organization: Geneva.
- World Health Organization. 2019. *Non-pharmaceutical public health measures for mitigating the risk and impact of epidemic and pandemic influenza*. World Health Organization: Geneva.
- Xiao J, Shiu EYC, Gao H, Wong J, Fong M, Ryu S, Cowling B. 2020. Nonpharmaceutical measures for pandemic influenza in nonhealthcare settings—personal protective and environmental measures. *Emerging Infectious Disease Journal* **26**: 967. <https://doi.org/10.3201/eid2605.190994>.
- Yañez A, Duggan J, Hayes C, Jilani M, Connolly M. 2017. PandemCap: decision support tool for epidemic management. In *2017 IEEE Workshop on Visual Analytics in Healthcare (VAHC)*. IEEE: Phoenix, AZ; 24–30. <https://doi.org/10.1109/VAHC.2017.8387497>.

Supporting information

Additional supporting information may be found in the online version of this article at the publisher's website.

Data S1. Supporting information.

Data S2. Supporting information.

Data S3. Supporting information.